

TRENDS in Pediatric Palliative Care Research (TPPCR) 2026; Issue #03: Commentary on

Bertaud, S. et al.

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Abstract:

This TPPCR commentary discusses the 2025 paper by Bertaud, S. et al., Hope pluralism in antenatal palliative care, *Journal of Medical Ethics: Journal of the Institute of Medical Ethics*.

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Prior to reading Bertaud et al.'s "Hope Pluralism in Antenatal Palliative Care," the term hope pluralism was not part of my vocabulary - though, in practice, I suspect I had long been engaging in it without naming it. Simply put, hope pluralism refers to the capacity to hold multiple hopes simultaneously. As a palliative oncologist who routinely navigates hope with patients and families in complex and emotionally fraught situations, I was eager to explore the parallels within the rapidly evolving field of antenatal palliative care.

The authors introduce the concept through the case of expectant parents who receive a life-limiting diagnosis for their unborn child. The parents respond with a familiar constellation of emotions: grief, disbelief, denial, and hope - particularly hope that the diagnosis is incorrect and that their child will be born healthy. It is this hope for a miracle that often precipitates moral and ethical distress among medical providers, who may question whether families fully understand the medical information being shared.¹ Bertaud and colleagues highlight the tension that arises when clinicians feel compelled to secure parental acknowledgment of a likely negative outcome. Yet hope is widely recognized as a positive coping strategy² and may even serve a protective function during bereavement.³ The authors therefore pose challenging questions including: Is there such a thing as "bad" or "inappropriate" hope? And can one have too much hope?

Hope is generally defined as a positive orientation toward a desired but uncertain future outcome.⁴ In contrast, "inappropriate hope" is often understood as hope that does not align with or respond to relevant clinical facts⁵ - an interpretation that frequently triggers provider distress. But who determines whether a particular hope is inappropriate? As antenatal medicine advances, particularly with the development of novel in utero interventions,^{6,7} prognostic uncertainty

persists and the boundaries of what is possible continue to shift. Patients and families retain the right to articulate hopes that differ from those of their medical teams.

How, then, should clinicians respond when hope appears misaligned with medical reality? This is where hope pluralism offers guidance. By asking families, “What are you hoping for?” and “What else are you hoping for?” clinicians can uncover the layered values and priorities that shape decision-making. Too often, clinicians fear that sharing prognostic information will extinguish hope. Evidence suggests otherwise. In fact, creating space for multiple hopes can help patients and families clarify realistic goals and, when necessary, transition from one goal to another.^{8,9} Importantly, acknowledging unrealistic hopes does not obligate clinicians to deliver medically nonbeneficial care - a distinction that may lie at the heart of much provider moral distress.

Recently, I was consulted on the case of a young adult undergoing bone marrow transplantation for a benign hematologic condition. The theoretical probability of cure exceeded 90%, and the patient’s goals were correspondingly aggressive. However, several post-transplant complications ensued, the most life-threatening of which was a disseminated fungal infection. As the clinical course worsened, discordance emerged among medical teams. Arguments for increasingly aggressive interventions centered on the singular hope for a miracle. Yet other hopes had been articulated: the desire for comfort and for meaningful interaction with family. It became distressing to witness how alignment with one dominant hope shaped clinical decisions to such a degree.

This experience left me reflecting on the balance between honoring hope and upholding our medical and ethical responsibilities. Perhaps it is not patients and families whose hopes require

scrutiny, but rather we, as clinicians, who must examine how we interpret and respond to them. Monitoring our own reactions to so-called “inappropriate” hope may allow us to better support families while maintaining professional integrity.

I believe hope is a beautiful and powerful force. It can offer strength and peace; it can create space for uncertainty in a way that feels humane and generous; it allows me to align meaningfully with those I serve. I do not believe I have the authority to judge another’s hope as appropriate or inappropriate. I do, however, believe that hope should not cloud my commitment to providing ethically sound and medically responsible care. Learning to hold that balance, I suspect, is a lifelong endeavor.

References

1. Roscigno CI, Savage TA, Kavanaugh K, et al. [Divergent views of hope influencing communications between parents and hospital providers](#). Qualitative health research. 2012;22(9):1232-1246.
2. Beng TS, Xin CA, Ying YK, et al. [Hope in palliative care: a thematic analysis](#). [Journal of palliative care](#). 2022;37(2):177-182.
3. de Andrade Alvarenga W, DeMontigny F, Zeghiche S, Verdon C, Nascimento LC. [Experience of hope: An exploratory research with bereaved mothers following perinatal death](#). Women and Birth. 2021;34(4):e426-e434.
4. Hill DL, Feudtner C. [Hope, hopefulness, and pediatric palliative care](#). 2016;
5. Nekolaichuk CL, Bruera E. [On the nature of hope in palliative care](#). Journal of palliative care. 1998;14(1):36-42.

6. Varthaliti A, Pergialiotis V, Theodora M, et al. [Advances in Fetal Surgery: A Narrative Review of Therapeutic Interventions and Future Directions](#). *Medicina*. 2025;61(7):1136.
7. Yasin R, Azhar M, Allahuddin Z, Das JK, Bhutta ZA. [Antenatal care strategies to improve perinatal and newborn outcomes](#). *Neonatology*. 2025;122(Suppl. 1):13-31.
8. Levine DR, CuvIELlo A, Nelson C, Lu Z, Mandrell BN, Baker JN. [Hope-colored glasses: perceptions of prognosis among pediatric oncology patients and their parents](#). *JCO Oncology Practice*. 2021;17(6):e730-e739.
9. Feudtner C, Carroll KW, Hexem KR, Silberman J, Kang TI, Kazak AE. [Parental hopeful patterns of thinking, emotions, and pediatric palliative care decision making: a prospective cohort study](#). *Archives of pediatrics & adolescent medicine*. 2010;164(9):831-839.